

Role of Media to Promote Secularism in India: A Critical Discussion

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Abstract: India is a major democratic state where community diversity exists in many forms. Linguistic, positional, natural, cultural, eating habits, clothing, etc. are among the various aspects of India's national solidarity. In the social system, the concepts of religion and neutrality are combined with Secularism. The analysis of money has become very controversial today. During the colonial period, attempts were made to strengthen the ideology of Secularism through the Indian independence movement for the purpose of liberation from the pseudo-authority of British rule. After the long journey through the social system, we have now reached the 21st century where the ideology of Secularism is limited to constitutional restrictions. Political parties have provoked minority communal riots and ethnic hatred for small political interests. Additionally, media and social media do not accept messages of pure religious ideology as carriers to promote the bias of political power parties, exacerbating religious intolerance.

Key Words: Secularism, religious tolerance, ethnic hatred, social media, political interests, Colonialism.

Introduction: India is a liberal, democratic, secular state. The Preamble to the Constitution of India declares India to be a welfare state, where Secularism means giving equal status to all religions. India's secular ideals represent the highest form of religious tolerance that strives to establish unity in diversity. Religious harmony is a part of India's long-standing tradition. Secularism is a very important concept for people of different religions and religious beliefs to live in harmony within Indian society. Secularism is one of the oldest ideals of traditional India. The influence of religion in India can never be ignored. In fact, religion carries a lot of significance and relevance in India. In independent India, this state, which is bound by different races, religions, castes, and cultural integration, has been protecting democratic values by highlighting its multicultural heritage. In a developing democratic country like India, we can see the impact of the media at every moment. Although the Indian Constitution legally recognizes religious bias as unconstitutional, the role of the media in promoting the ideals of Secularism in contemporary Indian society is gradually diminishing.

Review of literature:

1. "Secularism in India Constitution and Role of Media: Secularism" : Ramesh Kumar Sin- highlights that Secularism is a social force that not only highlights a form of tolerance in the context of India, but also opens up the pure form of Secularism of the media to the entire world society.
2. "Secularism and Secularity: Contemporary": A Kosmin and Aricla keysar- In this article, he focuses on the global perspective on Secularism as well as its significance in different cultural and political contexts.
3. "Secularism in India: A Constitutional Ideal" by Ragnuram Raju (Economic and Political Weekly, Vol.43, No.39, September 27, 2008) - his article, he explores various aspects of India's constitutional framework of Secularism.
4. "Secularism in India: Its cause and effect" by Hridoiyyoti Buragohain (International Journal of Current Advanced Research) Vol.80, September 28, 2019. This journal discusses the historical context of India as a multi-ethnic state, how India's majority Hindu nation influences the preservation of a secu-

lar state, and how the role of the media has been able to present the ideals of Secularism to the public.

5. “The Impact of Social Media on Regions Tolerance in India: A case study on the Digital Discourse in Religious Conflicts”: Tinumeren Ozukum In this article highlights how social media has become integral to our lives. It has played a significant role in molding religious and cultural world. In this contemporary situation, how social media has been used to create religious intolerance, communal riots, and fundamentalist forces. From which, the direction has been highlighted here in searching for the path of liberation of humanity.

Objective of the Study:

The main purpose of the discussion on the role of the media in promoting Secularism in India is to address issues that have not been covered in previous discussions, such as whether the media has a moral role to play in promoting Secularism, to what extent the media has faced the challenge of maintaining religious communal harmony in various sectors, and the media's tendency to cover communal riots in favor of the ruling party. All these aspects have not been addressed in previous discussions, which have created a gap.

The main objective and research questions of my research are to raise public awareness about what Secularism is how the media can promote the development of religious harmony, and how, despite attempts to establish religious freedom through various provisions of the Constitution and constitutional amendments, this unity is being destroyed in politics.

Methodology:

- Research Design Framework: This study adopts a qualitative approach to gain a better understanding of what Secularism in India means and its characteristics. The study uses secondary data to understand the role of media in promoting Secularism in India.
- Data Collection: To gain insight into this topic, information has been collected mainly from various articles, books, media sources, legitimate information for discussion in a larger context, and government reports.
- Data Analysis: The focus of this project was mainly on quantitative data, and this was accomplished through thematic analysis and transcript identification.
- Document Analysis: The results of the document analysis were primarily combined with qualitative data to provide better insight into the significance of Secularism and media in India.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Historical Background of Secularism:

During the British colonial period, after 200 years of rule, the British adopted the policy of 'divide and rule' to maintain the separation and hostility between Hindus and Muslims in India before independence in 1947. In independent India, the Hindu-Muslim conflict led to a situation where Muhammad Ali Jinnah implemented the Pakistan proposal, resulting in the establishment of Pakistan as an independent nation-state, which was marked by a bloody massacre that shocked history. Western Secularism has its roots in Renaissance Europe, where the separation of church and state was advocated, and individual rights were prioritized. On the other hand, Indian Secularism emerged from the diverse religious landscape of the past. India's long history of religious pluralism has led to the development of a secular framework to promote harmony and prevent religious discrimination among diverse religion, including Hinduism, Islam, Christianity, Sikhism, and Buddhism,

and others. In the later period, in order to prevent communal tensions and caste riots, the first PM of independent India, Dr. Jawaharlal Nehru, chose the principles of socialism as the ideal path to guide the governance of an independent democratic state in the right direction and presented the secular structure as the path to the progress of an ideal nation-state.

What is Secularism?

The term 'Secularism' was first used in 1851 by the British social reformer George Jacob Holyoake. G.J. Holyoake used the word 'Secularism' to describe his personal moral philosophy and an ideal concept of society and politics. It is based on reason and is concerned with the welfare of mankind. The concept of 'Secularism' in India is similar to the Vedic principle, which indicates the neutrality of the state towards religion. The Constituent Assembly of India took an active and constructive role in the matter of Secularism while framing the Constitution, thereby ensuring mutual respect, dignity, and safeguard for all faith. Vision the Father of the Nation, Mahatma Gandhi, and Secularism was based on a commitment to the unity of virtuous communities, which would be respectful of truth, and there was an emphasis on inquiry. On the contrary, the socialist Jawaharlal Nehru's idea of Secularism was based on scientific humanism. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar was Chairman of the Drafting Committee and Father of the Constitution, according to him Secularism did not mean religious discrimination, but rather the idea of a meeting place for all, regardless of race and religion, conveyed with a visionary view of historical development.

Role of Media:

The word 'media' was first used in the 1840s. It comes from a Latin word 'Medias', which means middle or intermediate. Known as the fourth pillar of democracy, the media is an essential and important part of modern community. Media play a crucial role in changing the superstructure of society and human behavior. Media influences public by providing people with information, education, entertainment, and various daily events, raising awareness of various issues. The media works to eliminate poverty, prejudice, religious discrimination, and bias from society. The media, especially television, radio, newspapers, etc., have been playing an active role in bringing about positive changes in the social system. In today's internet era, various webpages including blogs, Facebook, Twitter, and MySpace are being used to make people aware of various issues. In the Indian context, the media has been able to protect social cohesion by opposing discrimination based on religion, class, and color, promoting the message of Secularism to the people of India while maintaining equality, and evaluating the extent of its success and failures.

Implementation of Religious Neutrality in the Indian Constitution:

The Constitution of India assure right of conscience, freedom to profess, practice, and propagate religion to all citizens in several articles of the Constitution, including section three Fundamental Rights (Articles 12 to 35), Section four Directive Principles of the State (Article 36 to 51), and Section IV (51A) Fundamental Duties. For example:

- **Article 14** guarantees the protection of equal opportunities for all by law.
- **Article 16(1)** all citizens shall have equal opportunities in public service and shall be no discrimination on the grounds of creed, nation, color, gender, descent, or birth place.
- **Article 25** guarantees that everyone shall be equally entitled to freedom of

conscience, freedom to profess, practice, and propagate their religion.

- **Article 26** states that every religious community or group can run its own religious organizations and activities.
- **Article 27** It prevents the use of public funds to promote any specific on religious grounds.
- **Article 28** states that the participation of students in religious education classes in educational institutions is completely optional, but religious education in educational institutions funded by state resources has been completely banned.
- According to **Articles 29 and 30**, minority citizens can set up and run their preferred educational institution for the protection of their interests and for the sake of their culture.
- **In 1976, the 42nd Constitutional Reform Act** included three words 'secular', 'socialism', and 'unity' in the Preamble to the Constitution of India, which states that Secularism means establishment of a republican system of government that ensures mutual respect for all communities.

Directions given by the Judiciary of Independent India for the formation of a Secular State:

First of all, it should be noted that the word 'Secularism' is not static but a dynamic concept. The judiciary of India has always tried to implement the different meanings of Secularism practically by issuing numerous judgments and orders to highlight Secularism as an ideal. In the case of *Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala* (1973), the Chief Justice of India, S.M. Sikri, stated that Secularism is a core principle of the Constitution. In *Bombay v. Union of India* (1994), the Supreme Court explained the meaning of Secularism does not mean discriminatory treatment of any religion, but rather equal treatment of all religions. Secularism is one of the most important foundations of the Indian social system, from equality to justice. However, in recent times, the Supreme Court has been asked to remove the words 'socialist' and 'secular' from the preamble. Justice Sanjiv Khanna is the 51st Chief Justice of the Supreme Court of India and his division, ruled in two cases in 1973 and 1994 that Secularism is a cornerstone of the Constitution of India. The Constitution is an integral part of the basic structure, and its removal from the preamble is declared baseless and illegal.

The main Challenges on the path to Secularism are:

- **Politics over religion:** One of the main tenets of secular ideology is to keep religion separate from politics. In contemporary India, instead of maintaining this separation, politics is being conducted in relation to religion. The behavior of political leaders indulges in narrow religious beliefs to appease Muslim fundamentalism, going beyond the Shah Bano case verdict (1985) and the Muslim Women Protection of Rights on Marriage Act (1986), and select candidates by appealing to religious sentiments during elections.
- **Communal parties and organizations, Newspapers:** All these institutions in India foster communalism. Organizations like the BJP, Muslim League, Akali Dal, Jamaat-e-Islami, Vishwa Hindu Parishad, Shiv Sena, and the Muslim United Front claim to represent particular communities, while newspapers like *Organiser*, *Swastika*, *Akali Patrika*, *Sobat*, and *Sarasik* create communal tension and destroy the spirit of harmony.
- **Self-conscious population:** The various castes of India are very conscious of maintaining their identity. The upper castes are more conservative than the

lower castes. S.L.Sikri states that this sense of identity among the castes of India has created an obstacle in the path of Secularism.

- **Discriminatory Reservation:** The reservation policy mentioned in the Constitution of India is highly discriminatory. Special facilities are provided for the advancement of Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and other backward communities of India; however, special facilities are not provided for other communities, including Muslims and Sikhs, which creates bias in the communal sphere and becomes an obstacle on the path to Secularism.
- **Absence of a secular civil code:** On the path to Secularism, various laws are observed. For Hindus, the Hindu Marriage Act and the Protection of Women from Domestic Abuse Act (2005) have been introduced, while the laws for Muslims and other minority communities are not applicable. As a result, Muslims, especially women, have to face bias in government laws in a patriarchal society.
- **Lack of proper education:** There are no adequate educational institutions to instill true secular ideals among students. As a result, the insufficient infrastructure and the negative mindset of teachers, along with religious bias, are creating obstacles to the development of secular ideals in the youth society.
- **Politics of Religious Polarization:** Past events such as the 1992 Babri Masjid demolition, the 1984 anti-Sikh movement, the 1992 and 1993 Mumbai attacks, the 2002 Gujarat movement, the 2013 Muzaffarnagar action, and 2020 Delhi riots, the 'love jihad' narrative, and the acts of violence against interfaith couples have created discrimination in the religious sphere.
- **Citizenship Amendment Act 2019:** This Act provides citizenship is granted to Hindus, Buddhists, Jains, Parsis, and Christians from Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan who came to India before December 31, 2014. The CAA and NRC Act have deprived other ethnic groups by giving priority to specific religious groups, which does not uphold the principles of Secularism.

The ways to protect Secularism:

The Constitution of India aims for a secular state. Steps that can be taken to strengthen this concept are:

- **Education is an effective tool:** Education is an important means of changing the mindset of people. According to Swami Vivekananda, society should educate the nation in a way that enables the youth to become the leaders of the country; they will be the guides of the future.
- **Uniform Civil Code:** India's Secularism has ensured a uniform civil code for various religious groups based on religious beliefs. Uttarakhand was the first state to implement the UCC under section 44 of the Constitution. This is living example of the path of Secularism.
- **Separate religion from politics:** To ensure religious tolerance, politics cannot be influenced by religious casteism, communal politics, or vote bank politics stemming from petty political interests. Politics should never influence religion. Instead, politics should focus on the welfare of society. Religion should guide the creation of cultural tolerance and brotherhood among people.
- **Fight against religious extremism:** Religious extremism, fundamentalism, and arbitrariness must be firmly suppressed to unite in tolerant religious unity to confront religious extremism.
- **Safeguarding minority interests:** Minority communities must be ensured

equal access to economic opportunities, employment, and other resources.

- **Correct criteria for reservation:** The existing reservation system based on minorities should be abolished, and the criteria for poverty should be established in the social system.
- **Positive role in the media:** Correct messages should be conveyed to the general public in a secular manner. It is not enough to favor a particular political party or to influence the right news to raise the TRP (Television Rating Point) of Doordarshan's own organization. If you want to retain the trust of the people, the media must be correct, clear, and transparent. Only then can it be possible to overcome obstacles on the path of Secularism in society.

Why India needs Secularism and media transparency:

India has always been a diverse nation-state in terms of culture, religion, and diversity. Secularism is necessary in a country like India to keep people united across different religions, castes, and socio-cultural backgrounds. India is today the largest nation-state on the map of the entire world system, combining all religions. The country is a place where many nationalities and tribes live together. It has always refrained from religious wars between the church and the state, unlike Western countries. Secularism is the only tool to instill patriotism among minorities. However, it is true that although people have used religion as a political weapon for some time to fulfill their political interests, the sense of nationalism among the people has surpassed the communal one. Along with this, the media needs to create a stir among the people regarding the ideals of Secularism, national unity, sentiment, and brotherhood. When the media presents information correctly to the human race, society as a whole becomes a conscious, intelligent, educated community capable of making right decisions. People become the primary architects in building an ideal state. Therefore, the media's role in helping those architects recognize the difference between right and wrong is very relevant today.

Conclusion:

India is a country that respects diversity within the unity of a great nation, which includes more than 4,000 different races, religions, castes, languages, and communal practices. In this context, Amartya Sen has rightly commented on the pluralistic social system: 'Pride and respect are hidden in our differences and in our open-minded mentality.' Therefore, even though the era changes along the path of history, the sense of religious unity cherished by the traditions of the past will remain active in showing the direction of the future. In today's social system, it can be observed that, in some areas, Hinduism is seen as a madness among people in Ayodhya, centered on the birthplace of Ram, which is sometimes taken to extreme levels. Additionally, religious fundamentalism, casteism, violence, and religious wars have paved the way for this. Although many laws have been enacted to protect religious equality in our country, it appears that electoral politics is being undermined, while fundamentalism and petty political selfishness prevail. This system of petty interests is once again giving respect to certain communities of individuals who are included in the illiterate religious dogma present in the social system. Therefore, the responsibility of implementing Secularism properly in the 21st century lies with us, as well as with the state and government. The media must be proactive in conveying the message of the proper implementation of the uniform civil code, proper education of the people, and equality of entire religions to everyone. The gap between promise and effort must be bridged. The media must end all discrimination and be transparent and clear, and the voices of people who are vic-

tims of religious violence must be actively raised in every field of society without any bias. Only then will all discrimination be removed from the social system, and the media will become a real voice for the public.

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